

BLOOD FERRITIN LEVEL WHEN IRON OVERLOADED IN CHILDREN WITH B-THALASSEMIA**Hasanzadeh N.Ch.**

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The aim of this study was to determine the changes in serum iron and ferritin concentrations in patients with β -thalassemia receiving Desferal therapy. 125 patient with β -thalassemia was examined. 68 of them were boys and 53 were girls. The control group consisted of 20 healthy people. Depending on the clinical course of the disease, the examined patients were treated with desferal in different doses. After taking Desferal, the concentration of ferritin in the blood of patients was determined. Thus, the decrease in the concentration of ferritin depends on the dose of Desferal. Thus, the use of desferal therapy in the treatment of β -thalassemia patients has been shown to be appropriate. The determination of ferritin in the blood serum can play an important role in maintaining the normal level of liver and spleen function in this group of diseases, allowing for accurate selection of desferal dose dynamically.

Keywords: thalassemia, ferritin, desferal, β -thalassemia, iron

One of the main reasons for the development of complications in diseases that require regular replacement of the erythrocyte mass is iron deposition in organs and tissues [1,2]. Among these diseases, β -thalassemia has an important place [3,4]. β -Thalassemia is caused by a defect in the synthesis of only the β -chain, it is divided into β^+ thalassemia, in which the synthesis of the β -chain is preserved, and β^0 -thalassemia synthesis of the β -chain is completely absent. β^0 - and β^+ - thalassemia are characterized by the accumulation of iron in various organs [5]. The human body is well adapted to the accumulation of iron from the outside in iron deficiency states, or in anemia, as well as to a decrease in the utilization of iron from the macrophage system during inflammation [6].

It is possible to eliminate excess iron by using iron-removing compounds, i.e. drugs that can bind iron and remove it from the body [7]. The main medical iron chelator drug available to physicians is currently time is desferal (desferrioxamine) [8]. The optimal dose of Desferal can be calculated by determining the total amount of iron and ferritin received by the patient and the amount of metal excreted from the body as a result of the use of various doses of Desferal [9].

Materials and research methods. 125 patients (68 boys and 53 girls) with β -thalassemia major were under observation. The control group consisted of 20 healthy individuals. The diagnosis was made on the basis of the determination of the hemoglobin fractions HbA2 and HbF using the isoelectric focusing method on polyacryl-ampholine plastics with a pH of 3.5-9.5 using a Multiphor 2117 instrument from LKB (Sweden). The amount of ferritin was determined by enzyme immunoassay using a Stat Fax apparatus (USA).

Results. In patients with β -thalassemia, the amount of Hb is 3.4 times, erythrocytes - 1.76 times, hematocrit 1.5 times less than in healthy. Hemoglobin fractions in patients with β -thalassemia showed an increased level of HbF, it was found to be $60.5 \pm 2.1\%$, which is 42.6 times higher than in healthy individuals. The amounts of HbA2 in both groups were similar; in

patients $1.42 \pm 0.08\%$ (norm $2.07 \pm 0.14\%$). When studying iron metabolism in patients with β -thalassemia, an increased content of serum iron and ferritin was revealed. The level of serum iron in patients with β -thalassemia was increased 1.6 times, 33.7 ± 2.5 , serum ferritin was 2254.6 ± 186.3 31 times compared with the control group. After the first intake of Desferal, the average level of ferritin in the blood decreased to an average of 2734.3 ± 358.3 ng/l.

The mean blood ferritin level was 2452.3 ± 373.7 units in patients who received desferal for the second time (29 individuals). At the same time, in half of the cases, the ferritin level did not exceed the limit of 2000.0 units and in 25% of cases were less than 1119.0 units, while a quarter of the patients had rather high rates - more than 3076.0 units, in no patient the ferritin level did not exceed 9450 units. There was a significant difference from baseline ($p_U = 0.014$), which cannot be asserted from the level of the previous Desferal session ($p_U = 0.294$). A more detailed statistical analysis revealed a decrease in ferritin in all patients compared with the previous treatment session. ($p_W < 0.001$).

Conclusions. The regression model can help us to predict the process in further treatment sessions with 95% probability level. Thus, the results of the conducted laboratory studies indicate the expediency of using desferal therapy in the complex treatment of β -thalassemia major as effective. Determining the level of ferritin after each dose of Desferal is the main an indicator of iron stores in examined patients with β -thalassemia major.

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